

Horasani-zade dervish lodge (tekke) in Heraklion

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Established in 1650 under the patronage of Gazi Deli Hüseyin Pasha, the commander-in-chief of the Ottoman forces during the Cretan War (1645-1669), the Horasani-zade tekke was entrusted to Bektashi dervish sheikh Horasani-zade Mevlana Dervish Ali Dede. Originating from Kırşehir in central Anatolia, a place closely linked to Bektashism, he arrived in Crete during the Cretan War as the head of the Bektashi dervishes participating in the campaign. Upon his death in 1671 he was interred in a mausoleum (türbe) within the tekke garden. According to the accounts of Ottoman traveler Evliya Celebi, by the latter half of the 17th century, the tekke hosted 80 dervishes who provided communal meals and hospitality to visitors, while its scenic garden was ideal for leisurely walks. The tekke was abandoned and renovated several times. During a renovation that took place in 1811 by Sheikh Dervish Ali Baba, an additional fountain and a mosque were built. The tekke operated until the departure of the last Muslims from Crete in 1923-24. The mausoleum and the mosque are still preserved today.

Date Range: 1650 CE - 1924 CE

Region: Horasani-zade dervish lodge (tekke) in Heraklion

Region tags: Greece

Horasani-zade tekke, located in present-day Heraklion.

Status of Participants:

✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

General Variables

Sources and Excavations

Print Sources

Print sources used for understanding this subject:

- Source 1: Gülsoy, Ersin. *Girit'in Fethi ve Osmanlı İdaresinin Kurulması (1645-1670)*. Istanbul: Tatav, 2004.
- Source 2: Çelebi, Evliya. *Evliya Çelebi Seyahatnamesi*. Topkapı Sarayı Kütüphanesi Bağdat 308 Numaralı Yazmanın Transkripsiyonu - Dizini. Edited by Seyit Ali Kahraman, Yücel Dağlı, and Robert Dankoff. Vol. 8. Istanbul: Yapı Kredi Yayınları, 2003.
- Source 3: Köprülü, F. Orhan. "Usta-Zâde Yunus Bey'in Meçhul Kalmış Bir Makalesi: 'Bektaşiliğin Girid'de İntişarı.'" *Güney-Doğu Avrupa Araştırmaları Dergisi* 9 (1980): 37-86.

Online Sources

Online sources used for understanding this subject:

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– Source 1 URL: <https://explore.cure-project.gr>

Has this place been the focus of excavation (pre-modern, illicit, or scientific):

Answer 'Yes' for each period or type of excavation.

– No

Topographical Context

Is the place associated with a feature in the landscape

– Other [specify]: N/A

Does the place involve human-made features besides structure:

Other features might be ground clearing, terracing, other modifications of the local environment.

– No

Is the place situated in an urban or significantly urbanized area:

– Yes

Is there a distinct boundary between the place and the urban fabric:

– No

Is the place located significantly within the urban fabric:

Is the place centrally located, or at the crossroads of significant pathways?

– Yes

Is the place situated in a rural setting:

– Yes

Notes: The tekke was established in a rural area on the outskirts of Heraklion, where, during the Cretan War, the Ottomans had constructed the Inadiye fortress to serve the needs of the army during the conquest of Heraklion.

Are there settlements in close proximity to the place:

– Yes

- ↳ Are there routes of travel in close proximity to the place:
 - Yes

Is the place situated far removed from non-religious places of habitation:
– No

Structures Present

Are there structures or features present:

Instructions: Answer once for each structure/feature or group that can be differentiated.

– Yes

- ↳ A single structure
 - Yes

- ↳ The structure has a definite shape
 - Square

- ↳ One single feature
 - Other [specify]: N/A

- ↳ A group of structures:
 - No

- ↳ A group of features:
 - Yes

- ↳ Are they part of a single design/construction stage:
 - No

- ↳ Is it part of a larger place/sanctuary:
 - Yes

- ↳ What is the function of the structure/feature or group:
Answer "Yes" once for each distinct function
 - Worship

- ↳ Worship:
 - Communal

- ↳ Is the structure/feature finished:
 - Yes

- ↳ Was the structure/feature intended to last beyond a generation:
 - Yes

- ↳ Was the structure/feature modified through time:
 - Yes

- ↳ Was the structure/feature destroyed:
 - Yes

Notes: Parts of the structure were destroyed over time, but the mausoleum of its founder and the mosque are still preserved.

- ↳ How was the structure/feature destroyed
 - Collapsed

- ↳ Was it destroyed deliberately:
 - Other [specify]: N/A

- ↳ Was it destroyed by accident/natural phenomena:
 - Other [specify]: N/A

- ↳ Has the structure/feature been reconstructed:
 - Yes

- ↳ In antiquity
 - Periodically

Notes: The structure has been abandoned and renovated for several times from the late 17th until the early 20th century.

- ↳ In modernity
 - Post-Renaissance

Reasons for Creation/Construction/Consecration

Is the place used for the worship of/communication with non-human supernatural beings:

– Yes

Dedicated to a supernatural being:

– Yes [specify]: God

Dedicated to more than one supernatural being:

– No

Is the place used for the worship of a semi-divine human being:

– No

Is the place used for the worship of non-divine ancestors:

– No

Was the place commissioned/built by an official political entity:

A political entity is a local power structure that leverages a workforce.

– Yes

Specify

– Private individual

– Other [specify]: The commander-in-chief Gazi Deli Hüseyin Pasha funded its construction.

Were the Structures built by specific groups of people:

– Field doesn't know

Was the place thought to have originated as the result of divine intervention:

– Field doesn't know

Was the place created to mark or commemorate the birthplace of a supernatural or human being:

– No

Was the place created as the result of an event:

– Field doesn't know

Was the creation of the place sponsored by an external financial/material donation:

– Yes

Is this sponsor of the same religious group/tradition as the main usage of the place:

– Yes

Was the establishment of the place motivated by:

– Expression of devotion with no expectation of favor in return

Was the place built specifically for housing scriptures/sacred texts:

– No

Design and Material Remains

Overall Structure

Is the place made up of multiple built structures:

– Yes

Are any of the structures attached to or associated with a landscape feature:

– Yes

Are any of the structures attached to other structures:

– Yes

Is there a hierarchy among the structures:

– Yes

Is monumental architecture present:

Monumental architecture is defined here as a built structure that surpasses average human proportions and in general is larger and more complex than is necessary to fulfill the structure's utilitarian function(s). Examples of monumental architecture include Mesopotamian Ziggurats, Egyptian Pyramids, Greek and Roman temples, Mesoamerican Pyramids, North American and Aegean burial mounds, etc.

– No

Is the structure/feature made out of natural materials:

Answer [Yes] for each material type

– Yes

↳ Earth
– No

↳ Sand
– No

↳ Clay
– No

↳ Plaster
– No

↳ Wood
– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:
– Yes

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:
– No

↳ Grass
– No

↳ Stone
– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:
– Yes

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:
– No

↳ Other
– Other [specify]: N/A

Is the structure/feature made out of human-made materials

– No

Decoration

Is decoration present:

– Yes

↳ Is decoration part of the building (permanent):

– Yes

↳ On the outside:

– Yes

Notes: A quranic inscription is carved above the mosque's entrance.

↳ On the inside:

– Yes

↳ Is decoration attached to the building, i.e. movable reliefs or tapestries

– No

↳ Is the decoration figural:

A figural representation is defined here as one that contains the depiction of discernible human, anthropomorphic, animal, or zoomorphic forms. In general, it differentiates between animate and inanimate beings, as well as between narrative compositions and still life, landscapes, abstraction, etc. Answer [Yes] for each type of figure depicted

– No

↳ Is the decoration non-figural:

– Yes

↳ Is it geometric/abstract

– Yes

↳ Floral motifs

– No

↳ Is it writing/caligraphy

– Yes

↳ Other [Specify]

–Other [specify]: N/A

↳ Is the decoration hidden or restricted from view:

– No

↳ Are there statues present:

– No

↳ Are there reliefs present:

A relief as opposed to sculpture carved on the round is a work of sculpture in which the figures project from a background support, generally a flat surface. Reliefs can be carved out of stone, clay, or a similar material.

– No

↳ Are there paintings present:

– No

↳ Are there mosaics present:

– No

↳ Are there inscriptions as part of the decoration:

– Yes

↳ Are the inscriptions ornamental:

– Yes

↳ Are the inscriptions informative/declarative
[e.g. historical narratives, calendars, donor lists etc...]

– Yes

↳ Are the inscription a formal dedication:

– Yes

↳ Other [Specify]

–Other [specify]: A quranic inscription above the mosque's entrance is carved in relief.

↳ Other type of decoration:

– Field doesn't know

Iconography

Are there distinct features in the places iconography:

– No

Beliefs and Practices

Funerary Associations

Is this place a tomb/burial:

– Yes

Notes: The mausoleum of Horasani-zade Mevlana Dervish Ali Dede is included in the structure.

Is this a place for the worship of the dead:

– No

Is this a place for treatment of the corpse:

– No

Are co-sacrifices present in tomb/burial:

Co-sacrifices are animal/human sacrifices prompted by the death of the primary occupant of the tomb/burial.

– No

Are grave goods present:

– No

Are formal burials present:

– No

Supernatural Beings

Is a supreme high god is present:

– Yes

Notes: A supreme high god is worshipped.

↳ Are they anthropomorphic:

– No

↳ Are they sky deity:

– No

↳ Are they chthonic (underworld)

– No

↳ Are they fused with king/kingship role (king = high god)

– No

↳ Are they the monarch is seen as a manifestation or emanation of the high god:

– No

↳ Are they kin relation to elites:

– No

↳ Are they other type of loyalty or connection to elites:

– No

↳ Are they unquestionably good:

– I don't know

↳ Are they other:

– Other [specify]: N/A

Does the supreme high god communicate with the living at this place:

– Yes

↳ In waking, everyday life:

– Yes

↳ In dreams:

– Yes

↳ In trance possession:

– Yes

↳ Through divination practices:

– Yes

↳ Only through religious specialists:

– No

↳ Only through monarch:

– No

↳ Other

–Other [specify]: N/A

Are previously human spirits present:

– No

Do human spirits communicate with the living at this place:

– No

Are nonhuman supernatural beings present:

– Yes

Notes: In some Sufi lodges, practitioners may believe in the presence of supernatural spirits, such as jinns or angels.

↳ Nonhuman spirits can be seen:

– Yes

↳ Nonhuman spirits can be physically felt:

– Yes

Do nonhuman spirits communicate with the living at this place:

– Yes

Notes: In certain Sufi lodges, practitioners may believe that spirits, such as jinns or angels, may communicate with the living through spiritual experiences.

↳ In waking, everyday life:

– Yes

↳ In dreams:

– Yes

↳ In trance possession:

– Yes

↳ Through divination practices:

– Yes

↳ Only through religious specialists:

– No

↳ Only through monarch:

– No

↳ Other

–Other [specify]: N/A

Are mixed human-divine beings present:

– Yes

Notes: In some Sufi lodges, individuals who are believed to have attained a high spiritual state may be considered as embodying both human and divine qualities, but they are not seen as divine beings themselves.

↳ Mixed human-divine spirits can be seen:

– Yes

↳ Mixed human-divine spirits can be physically felt:

– Yes

Do mixed human-divine beings communicate with the living at this place:

– Yes

↳ In waking, everyday life:

– Yes

↳ In dreams:

– Yes

↳ In trance possession:

– Yes

↳ Through divination practices:

– Yes

↳ Only through religious specialists:

– No

↳ Only through monarch:

– No

↳ Other

– Other [specify]: N/A

Is the supernatural being/high god present in the form of a cult statue(s):

– No

Supernatural Interactions

Is supernatural monitoring present:

– No

Do visitors communicate with the gods or supernatural beings:

– No

Ritual and Performance

Do rituals occur at this place:

Rituals are visibly enacted behaviors by one or more people for the purposes of religious observance.

– Yes

↳ Do large-scale rituals take place:

– No

↳ Do small-scale rituals take place:

– Yes

↳ On average how many participants are present in large-scale rituals:

– specify: It varies

↳ How often do these rituals take place:

– specify: Regularly

↳ Are there orthodoxy checks:

– No

↳ Are there orthopraxy checks:

– No

↳ Are there synchronic practices:

– Yes

↳ Are there intoxicants used during the ritual:

– Yes

Sacrifices, Offerings, and Maintenance

Are sacrifices performed at this place:

– No

Are there self-sacrifices present:

– No

Are material offerings present:

– No

Is attendance to worship/sacrifice mandatory:

– No

Is maintenance of the place performed:

– I don't know

Pilgrimage and Festivals

Are pilgrimages present:

– No

Is this place a venue for feasting:

– No

Are festivals present:

– I don't know

Divination and Healing

Is divination present:

– No

Is healing present/practiced at this place:

– No

Institutions and Scriptures

Religious Specialists

Are religious specialists present/in charge of this place:

Religious specialists are individuals whose primary duties within a population group are not concerned with subsistence or craft production but the maintenance of the religious landscape and culture of the group.

– Yes

Present full time

– Yes

↳ Present part time

– Yes

↳ Are the religious specialists of specific sex/gender:

– Yes

↳ Are the religious specialists of specific ethnicity:

– No

↳ Are the religious specialists of specific class/cast:

– Yes

↳ Are religious specialists dedicated to the place for life:

– Yes

↳ Are the religious specialists stratified in a hierarchical system:

– Yes

↳ Is access within the space segregated by this hierarchy:

– No

Does this place incorporate a living space for religious specialists:

– Yes

Notes: The tekke incorporated living quarters for the dervishes.

Is this place used for the training of religious specialists:

– Yes

Are there formal institutions for the maintenance of the place:

Institutions that are authorized by the religious community or political leaders

– Yes

Notes: The income of a wakf was dedicated for the maintenance of the tekke.

Bureaucracy

Is there a formal bureaucracy present at this place:

A bureaucracy consists of a hierarchical system of accounting and rule maintenance primarily concerned with material wealth.

– No

Does this place control economic resources (land, goods, tools):

– Yes

↳ Is this control the primary supporting income of this place:

– Yes

↳ Does this place lease out land:

– Yes

↳ Does this place lease out tools:

– Field doesn't know

Public Works

Does this place serve as a location for services to the community:

– Yes

↳ Public food distribution and/or storage:

– Yes

↳ Place for civic functions (census, elections, others):

– No

↳ Place for the practice of justice (trials, executions, etc.):

– No

↳ Function for water management:

– No

↳ Part of the transportation network:

– No

↳ Other

–Other [specify]: N/A

Writing/Scriptures

Is non-religious writing stored at this place:

Economic documents, records etc.

– No

Are there scriptures associated with this place:

– Yes

↳ Are they written:

– Yes

↳ Are they written at this place:

– No

↳ Are they oral:

– Yes

↳ Is there a story associated with the origin and/or construction of this place:

– No

↳ Are there religious specialists in charge of interpreting the scriptures:

– Yes

↳ Are the scriptures part of the building/place:

– Yes

↳ Attached to the structures as decoration:

– Yes

↳ Housed within the place/structure:

– Yes

↳ As dedicatory inscription(s):

– Yes

↳ Other

–Other [specify]: N/A

Bibliography

General References

Reference: Horasani-zade dervish lodge (tekke) in Heraklion, Gülsoy, Ersin. *Girit'in Fethi Ve Osmanlı İdaresinin Kurulması (1645-1670)*. Istanbul: Tatav, 2004.

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Reference: Horasani-zade dervish lodge (tekke) in Heraklion, Limnidi, Katerina. "Dervishes at the time of the cretan war: the establishment and operation of the tekke of horasani-zade (1650-1711)". University of Crete, 2014.